

Redox Cycling on Unmodified Gold Interdigitated Ultramicroelectrode Arrays for Interferent Free Electrochemical Detection of Pyocyanin

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1 **ABSTRACT:** Pyocyanin (PYO) is a quorum-sensing signalling molecule that is secreted exclusively by *Pseudomonas*
2 *aeruginosa* (*P. aeruginosa*). The monitoring of PYO concentrations can therefore be used to readily detect the presence of
3 *P. aeruginosa*. Dissolved oxygen interference has hampered the use of materials for sensors, such as gold, for PYO detection,
4 unless degassing of samples is incorporated, limiting point of care applicability. To this end, carbon-based electrodes are
5 typically employed but are limited in terms of reproducibility and miniaturisation. In this work we report oxygen
6 interference free electrochemical detection of PYO using an unmodified gold interdigitated array. Through the use of redox
7 cycling, dissolved oxygen interference was minimised, and highly sensitive detection was achieved in both buffered
8 conditions (73.4 nM) and real-world samples (100 nM). Additionally, multiple strains of *P. aeruginosa* were investigated and
9 the sensor was found to be highly accurate for all three strains (PA17, PA40, PA41) and demonstrated good agreement with
10 the typical UV-Vis detection method employed. This approach demonstrates the potential for future point of care testing
11 for PYO, and thereby *P. aeruginosa*, using these sensors, without the need for sample modification.

12 Introduction

13 *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is a ubiquitous, opportunistic gram-negative bacterium responsible for over 500,000
14 deaths annually, primarily as an agent of Healthcare Associated Infection (HAI)¹. Individuals with pathological
15 conditions such as burns, cystic fibrosis (CF) or those who are immunocompromised are particularly susceptible
16 to this antibiotic resistant ESKAPE pathogen.^{1,2} The World Health Organization has labelled the bacterium as a
17 high priority pathogen for new research.³ Similarly, the US Department of Health considers *P. aeruginosa* a
18 “serious threat”.⁴ The ability of this bacterium to form biofilms is also a major virulence factor. It is particularly
19 problematic for patients with lung conditions, especially cystic fibrosis, with 80% of CF patients experiencing
20 *Pseudomonas* infections.^{5,6} However, *P. aeruginosa* is more commonly observed in infected wounds, as one of
21 the most commonly occurring pathogens in chronic infections and burn victims.⁷⁻¹⁰ Notably these infections are
22 increasing in prevalence globally, and as such, there is an ever-increasing need for accurate *P. aeruginosa*
23 detection.^{7,11-14}

24 To date *Pseudomonas* detection has typically been performed using a combination of laboratory techniques,
25 such as plate culture, polymerase chain reaction, Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent Assay or high-performance
26 liquid chromatography.¹⁵⁻¹⁹ These methods are time consuming and are not suitable for portable use, limiting
27 point-of-care (POC) detection, which is crucial for preventing infections worsening.

28 A key issue with this bacterium, is its ability to form biofilms, which is directly influenced by the secretion of
29 pyocyanin. Pyocyanin is a quorum-sensing molecule that is one of the signals for biofilm formation and is
30 exclusively secreted by *P. aeruginosa*, with up to 95% of *Pseudomonas* strains producing pyocyanin.²⁰ As such,
31 the presence of pyocyanin can elucidate the presence of this problematic bacterium. Pyocyanin is a redox-active
32 molecule that typically exists in its zwitterionic form at neutral pH (7.0). In this form, pyocyanin displays a
33 distinct bright blue colour, however, when oxidised this colour shifts to a deep red. Both forms of the redox-
34 active molecule pyocyanin are readily detectable using spectroscopy, with UV-Vis absorption spectra typically
35 used. However, samples normally must be pre-treated or purified using chloroform extraction prior to
36 spectroscopic methods, again limiting POC potential.^{19,21-23}

37 Electrochemical sensors offer an attractive alternative to address these issues, with their usefulness having been
38 demonstrated for a wide variety of electroactive analytes.²⁴⁻²⁷ Consequently, due to its redox-active nature,
39 electrochemical detection of pyocyanin has begun to emerge as a promising candidate, having been
40 demonstrated using a variety of electrode materials, such as gold and carbon. While gold electrodes have

41 typically been able to achieve low limits of detections, a major drawback in their utilisation is the requirement
42 to either degas solutions, or complex modifications to eliminate oxygen interference. ²⁸⁻³¹ This has limited the
43 implementation of Au electrodes in POC devices.

44 Carbon, however, does not require degassing for pyocyanin detection and as such has been used prevalently. ³¹⁻
45 ³⁵ However, carbon electrodes have either been unable to achieve miniaturisation, e.g. screen-printed electrodes,
46 or suffer from electrode reproducibility/fouling/short lifetimes. ^{36,37}

47 In this work, we demonstrate a novel interdigitated gold ultramicroelectrode array capable of eliminating oxygen
48 interference through redox cycling. This enables facile pyocyanin detection without the need for degassing of
49 solutions, electrode modification or sample pre-treatment, lending itself to potential POC applications. Briefly,
50 reduction of both pyocyanin and the dissolved oxygen interferent occurs at working electrode 1 (WE1), the
51 generator, with the reduced pyocyanin species diffusing to working electrode 2 (WE2), the collector, whereupon
52 it is oxidised back into the original pyocyanin species. This oxidative peak is free from interference due to a
53 constant potential bias of -0.4 V vs Pt reference electrode, (outside the dissolved oxygen area of activity), leading
54 to an interferent free pyocyanin redox cycled signal. This method of oxygen interference removal, akin to that of
55 Seymour et al, was compared to degassed samples to confirm its efficacy. ³⁸

56 This sensor is capable of operating in both buffer and more complex media, such as nutrient broth, both above
57 and below the clinically relevant concentration range for wound management, (1-50 μM) and also surpasses the
58 upper limit imposed for high concentration sputum samples (130 μM). We demonstrate a LOD in ideal buffered
59 solution of 73.4 nM, with a LOD in real sample matrices determined to be 100 nM, both of which are far lower
60 than the clinically relevant lower limit. We performed detection in the linear range of 1-200 μM and 5-200 μM
61 for the buffered and real samples respectively, suggesting potential future applications for POC testing in both
62 wound management and sputum sample analysis.

63 **EXPERIMENTAL SECTION**

64 **Electrode Fabrication**

65 Silicon chip-based devices were fabricated as described by O'Sullivan et al, except for the counter electrode which
66 was changed to Pt instead of Au. ³⁹ Further information on fabrication is available in SI.

67

68 **Bacterial strains cultivation conditions and UV-Vis measurements**

69 Three clinical isolates of *P. aeruginosa* (PA41, PA40 and PA17), previously characterised for their pyocyanin
70 producing ability, were employed to test the response of the biosensor under conditions more relevant to a real-
71 world scenario.⁴⁰ Bacterial strains were cultivated in 100 mL static Nutrient Broth (Oxoid UK) cultures at 37 °C
72 for 72 hours. Following incubation, bacteria were removed from the broth by centrifugation at 7,000 x g for 15
73 minutes at 10 °C. Approximately 30 mL of supernatant was carefully decanted and filtered through a 0.2 µm
74 membrane filter to ensure cell removal prior to biosensor analysis. UV-Vis measurement details are available in
75 SI.

76

77 **Materials**

78 Ferrocene carboxylic acid (FCA), sodium phosphate monobasic, sodium phosphate dibasic and powdered
79 pyocyanin (98% HPLC Grade from *Pseudomonas Aeruginosa*) were all purchased from Merck (Ireland). All
80 solutions were prepared with DI water with resistivity of 18 MΩ cm⁻¹. A phosphate buffer (PB) solution was
81 prepared using 268.8 mg sodium phosphate monobasic and 110.2 mg sodium phosphate dibasic, then making
82 this solution up to 1 L using deionised water. This generated a pH 7.4 10 mM solution of PB, which was used for
83 all pyocyanin standard solution generation.

84 **Sample Degassing**

85 To perform measurements with a minimum of dissolved oxygen present in solution, samples were degassed by
86 sparging the solution with N₂ gas for 30 minutes. Degassing was performed using a dedicated N₂ gas line, with a
87 pipette tip placed within the solution to bubble N₂ gas throughout the solution. The solution was placed in a
88 beaker with a parafilm seal to minimise environmental exposure. Analysis was performed immediately after
89 degassing to ensure maximum accuracy.

90 **Results**

91 Figure 1 (a) shows the overall silicon chip device containing three sensors (each containing two IDEs), microSD
92 contact pads, interconnection tracks and the on-chip counter and reference electrodes. Figure 1 (b) shows an
93 optical micrograph of one such sensor, at a 50x optical magnification. The generator comb is connected to the
94 left-hand side, with 33 electrodes, whereas the collector comb is connected on the right-hand side with 34

95 electrodes. The additional tine on the collector was incorporated to ensure maximum collection efficiency. This
96 interdigitated geometry enables redox cycling, i.e. generation of a species at WE₁ via oxidation or reduction
97 followed by diffusion to WE₂ where it subsequently converted back into its original form via the opposite
98 reaction.

99
100 *Figure 1: (a) Overall view of microchip with 3x sensors and (b) 50x optical micrograph of one of these sensors*

101 Figure 2 (a) shows a typical CV of 1 mM ferrocene monocarboxylic acid (FCA) for a single working IDE vs on-
102 chip Pt RE. The working electrode was cycled from -0.15 V to 0.45 V at a scan rate of 50 mV/s. Four concurrent
103 measurements were performed, with the first disregarded as a conditioning step and the subsequent three
104 averaged to generate the CV response shown. Diffusion limited behaviour is readily observed, with a drop in
105 anodic current after the initial oxidative peak. This initial oxidative peak shows the conversion of the nearby FCA
106 molecules to FCA⁺, with the subsequent drop in current due to diffusion limited mass transport limitations. In
107 this scenario, fresh analyte must diffuse from the bulk solution to the sensor, causing a time lag, after which a
108 steady state current is reached, whereby subsequent increases in potential applied do not increase the current
109 response. Figure 2 (b) shows the same measurement, but with a second working electrode connected and held
110 at a potential bias of -0.15 V. In this approach, WE₂ continually reduces any generated FCA⁺ back into the original
111 FCA state. This allows a single molecule of analyte to be detected multiple times by means of redox cycling,
112 surmounting the mass-transport limitations previously seen, while greatly increasing the observed current
113 response. By comparing the peak current observed at the generator (WE₁), I_{gen} , and the collector (WE₂), I_{col} , a
114 collection efficiency (CE) for this redox cycling can be determined, using equation 1. In the case of FCA detection
115 this is the current observed at a potential of 0.45 V. The collection efficiency for this sensor was calculated to be
116 93.9%, suggesting very effective cycling at this current electrode geometry.

117

$$CE = -\frac{I_{col}}{I_{gen}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

118

119 *Figure 2: CVs of gold electrode array in a solution of 1 mM FCA in 10 mM PB. Each CV shown is an average of 3 scans.*
 120 *CVs were performed from -0.15 V to 0.45 V at 50 mV/s. CVs were performed in both (a) non-GC mode and (b) GC mode,*
 121 *with a potential bias of -0.15 V applied to WE2.*

122 Figure 3 (a) shows multiple Linear sweep voltammograms (LSVs) for both a blank measurement, performed in
 123 PB, and for detection of 10 μM pyocyanin in PB, using a single working electrode, i.e. non-GC mode. Each
 124 measurement consisted of four concurrent LSVs, with the first initial scan disregarded as a conditioning step
 125 and the subsequent three cycles averaged to generate the LSV shown. The working electrode (WE₁) potential
 126 was swept from -0.2 V to -0.8 V vs on-chip Pt reference electrode, at 50 mV/s. The reductive current observed in
 127 the blank (black line) shows that even when no pyocyanin is present, a large current response is observed. This
 128 is due to the presence of dissolved oxygen (DO). Unfortunately, this peak limits the ability to detect pyocyanin
 129 accurately as the DO concentration is typically unknown, also no sharp peak was visible when 10 μM pyocyanin
 130 was measured with oxygen present (red line). Typically, this can be remedied by degassing the solution, i.e., by
 131 bubbling nitrogen through the solution prior to measurement, enabling the reductive peak to be observed (blue
 132 line). However, the need to degas samples prior to analysis severely limits the portable application potential of
 133 this technology. To address this, an alternative method, redox cycling, may be employed. In this approach, WE₁
 134 is first employed to reduce both pyocyanin and the DO, respectively. These reductions are shown in equation 2
 135 and 3 for the pyocyanin and the dissolved oxygen respectively.

138

139 The reversible electrochemical reduction of pyocyanin is a two-electron transfer process, described in equation
 140 2, Upon reduction of PYO and DO, both reduced forms of these molecules then diffuse to WE₂ where oxidation

141 of the reduced pyocyanin species, only, occurs and is thus free from oxygen interference, as shown in Figure 3
 142 (b). To achieve this, a potential bias of -0.4 V was applied to WE2 as this is too anodic, i.e., outside of the oxygen
 143 reduction potential window, thereby ensuring WE2 would not perform any oxygen reduction, but was sufficient
 144 to oxidise reduced pyocyanin molecules. The blank measurement (black line) clearly shows that there is no
 145 interfering oxygen reducing current, thereby allowing sensitive detection of pyocyanin. Furthermore, when
 146 comparing the 10 μM sample (red line), to a degassed version of this sample (blue line) there is little to no
 147 variance from between samples, with the slight deviation being attributed to experimental variances. These
 148 results confirm that the redox cycling method for removing oxygen interference is effective, enabling pyocyanin
 149 detection without the need to degas solutions. Figure 3 (c) shows a schematic of this redox method. The
 150 generator, shown in blue, initially reduces both the dissolved oxygen (O_2) and pyocyanin (PYO), with subsequent
 151 diffusion to a collector. The collector, shown in red, then re-oxidises the generated species (PYO^{2-}) back into
 152 pyocyanin, with no interference from the dissolved oxygen. Consequently, this approach allows for facile
 153 detection without the requirement for sample preparation.

154

155 Figure 3: LSVs of 10 mM PB blank (black line), 10 μM PYO in 10 mM PB (red) and 10 μM PYO in 10 mM PB after
 156 degassing (blue), vs Pt reference electrode, at a scan rate of 50 mV/s. Each LSV represents three averaged scans. For
 157 (a) non-GC mode and (b) GC mode with a bias of -0.4 V applied at WE2. (c) Schematic of redox cycling, with generator

158 in blue and collector in red. Reduction of dissolved oxygen and pyocyanin occurs at generator, with oxidation of only
159 this reduced pyocyanin occurring at the collector, thereby removing the dissolved oxygen interference

160 Having optimised this approach, a calibration was performed in 10 mM PB, using the previously mentioned
161 parameters, and the collection current versus potential (of the generator) is shown in Figure 4 (a). Various
162 concentrations of pyocyanin, from 1-200 μM , were analysed and the resultant calibration plot is presented in
163 Figure 4 (b). The increase in observed oxidative current at WE2 was shown to be highly linear ($R^2 = 0.997$) with
164 pyocyanin concentration over a wide μM range. The limit of detection (LOD) for this method of 73.4 nM was
165 calculated using equation 4, where σ_{blank} is the standard deviation of the blank and m is the slope of the
166 calibration. This LOD is significantly lower than the required clinical range, demonstrating the potential for
167 accurate POC measurements with this system. Error bars are included in the data points but are extremely tight.

168
$$LOD = 3.3 \frac{\sigma_{blank}}{m} \quad (4)$$

169

170 Figure 4: (a) LSVs of various concentrations of pyocyanin vs Pt reference electrode. Each CV represents 3 averaged
171 scans for the oxidative current observed at WE2, when a bias of -0.4 V is employed. (b) Shows the calibration generated
172 from this data

173 Having demonstrated sensitive detection in buffered conditions, pyocyanin detection was then undertaken in
174 cell nutrient broth samples, using a serial standard addition approach. A stock solution of pyocyanin was first
175 prepared in 10 mM PB, and appropriate aliquots of this added to nutrient broth to yield various concentrations
176 in the range of 5-200 μM . All detection parameters were maintained as for the buffered samples. Figure 5 (a)
177 shows typical LSVs for these broth samples. Again, each measurement consisted of four concurrent linear sweep
178 voltammograms, with the first initial scan disregarded as a conditioning step and the subsequent three scans
179 averaged. The measured oxidative current at each concentration was slightly lower in the broth when compared

180 to the buffered counterparts in Figure 4 (a). This may be due to the complex matrix of nutrient broth having a
 181 higher ionic strength altering double-layer capacitance, thereby reducing the current sensitivity or some slight
 182 fouling of the electrode. However, Figure 5 (b) shows the resultant calibration plot for the nutrient broth. The
 183 plot was highly linear ($R^2 = 0.995$), similar to the buffered samples in Figure 4 (b). All data points consisted of
 184 an average of three LSVs. Error bars are included but are too small to be seen in all but the 200 μM data point.
 185 Using the same calculation method (equation 2), with the standard deviation of the blank, the LOD was
 186 determined to be 100 nM, a slight decrease when compared to buffered samples, though still below the required
 187 clinical lower limit.

188

189 *Figure 5: (a) LSVs of serial addition of pyocyanin vs Pt reference electrode, in nutrient broth. Each LSV represents 3*
 190 *averaged scans for the oxidative current observed at WE2, when a bias of -0.4 V is employed. (b) Calibration generated*
 191 *from this data*

192 Finally, to confirm the accuracy of this system, real world samples were generated using a variety of strains and
 193 sensor performance compared to the more-traditional UV-Vis method; the results of which are shown in Table
 194 1. To confirm the efficacy of the UV-Vis approach various concentrations were first tested as shown in Figure S1,
 195 before the real sample analysis. Further information on the real samples can be seen in SI, in particular Table S1
 196 and Figure S2. Overall good agreement was observed between both methods for all strains, confirming the
 197 accuracy of this method for pyocyanin detection.

Sample	Sensor (μM)	UV-Vis (μM)
PA41 72h	17.43	19.00
PA40 72h	19.22	22.25
PA17 72h	16.96	18.19

198 *Table 1: Various real-world samples of differing strains of P. aeruginosa, with pyocyanin concentrations determined*
199 *both by electrochemical sensor and UV-vis method.*

200 **Conclusions**

201 We have developed a novel method for electrochemical removal of oxygen interference in pyocyanin detection
202 based on redox cycling at interdigitated gold microband arrays. This method was benchmarked against UV-vis
203 gold standard method from literature, with excellent agreement between both methods. This sensor accuracy
204 was also coupled with highly sensitive detection, with an LOD of 73.4 nM in ideal buffered samples, and an LOD
205 of 100 nM in real world complex sample matrices obtained. The lack of sample pre-treatment required in this
206 method, i.e., no oxygen removal or extraction utilising HCl as in the UV-Vis method, demonstrates the potential
207 for future applications in point of care testing with this system.

208 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

209 **Shane O'Sullivan:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review and
210 editing.

211 **David Fox:** Methodology

212 **Megan Taggart:** Methodology

213 **James Dooley:** Conceptualization, Methodology and Writing -review and editing

214 **Sasitharan Balasubramaniam:** Conceptualization

215 **Alan O'Riordan:** Conceptualization, Writing -review and editing and Supervision, funding

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